

neurogenetics

Celia's encephalopathy and c.974dupG in BSCL2 gene: a hidden change in a known variant.

--Manuscript Draft--

Manuscript Number:	NEGE-D-18-00135R1	
Full Title:	Celia's encephalopathy and c.974dupG in BSCL2 gene: a hidden change in a known variant.	
Article Type:	Original Article	
Keywords:	BSCL2; seipin; PELD; neurodegeneration; congenital generalized lipodystrophy; cryptic splicing	
Corresponding Author:	David Araujo-Vilar Universidade de Santiago de Compostela Santiago de Compostela, SPAIN	
Corresponding Author Secondary Information:		
Corresponding Author's Institution:	Universidade de Santiago de Compostela	
Corresponding Author's Secondary Institution:		
First Author:	Sofia Sánchez-Iglesias	
First Author Secondary Information:		
Order of Authors:	Sofia Sánchez-Iglesias	
	Melissa Crocker	
	Mar O'Callaghan	
	Alejandra Darling	
	Angels García-Cazorla	
	Rosario Domingo-Jiménez	
	Ana I. Castro	
	Antía Fernández-Pombo	
	Alvaro Ruibal	
	Pablo Aguiar	
	Miguel Garrido-Pumar	
	Antonio Rodríguez-Núñez	
	Julian Álvarez-Escudero	
	Rebecca J. Brown	
David Araujo-Vilar		
Order of Authors Secondary Information:		
Funding Information:	Instituto de Salud Carlos III (PI10/02873)	Prof. David Araujo-Vilar
	Instituto de Salud Carlos III (PI13/00314)	Prof. David Araujo-Vilar
	Secretaria Xeral de Investigación e Desenvolvemento, Xunta de Galicia (10PXIB208013PR)	Prof. David Araujo-Vilar
	Secretaria Xeral de Investigación e Desenvolvemento, Xunta de Galicia (ED341b 2017/19)	Prof. David Araujo-Vilar

	Fundación Mutua Madrileña (Call 2015)	Prof. David Araujo-Vilar
	Asociación Española de Familiares y Afectados de Lipodistrofias (AELIP) (2018)	Dr Sofía Sánchez-Iglesias
	National Institute of Diabetes and Digestive and Kidney Diseases (US) (2018)	Dr Rebecca J. Brown
Abstract:	<p>Celia's encephalopathy (Progressive Encephalopathy with/without Lipodystrophy, PELD) is a childhood neurodegenerative disorder with a fatal prognosis before the age of 10, due to the variant c.985C>T in the BSCL2 gene that causes a cryptic splicing site leading to skipping of exon 7. For years, different authors have reported cases of congenital generalized lipodystrophy due to the variant c.974dupG in BSCL2 associated with neurological manifestations of variable severity, although some of them clearly superimposable to PELD. Aim: To identify the molecular mechanisms responsible for these neurological alterations in two patients with c.974dupG. Subjects and Methods: Clinical characterization, biochemistry and neuroimaging studies of two girls carrying this variant. In silico analysis, PCR amplification and BSCL2 cDNA sequencing. BSCL2-201 transcript expression, which lacks exon 7, by qPCR in fibroblasts from the index case, from a healthy child as a control and from two patients with PELD, and in leukocytes from the index case and her parents. Results: One of the children presented with a severe encephalopathy including a picture of intellectual deficiency, severe language impairment, myoclonic epilepsy and lipodystrophy as described in PELD, dying at 9 years and 9 months of age. The other 2-year-old patient showed incipient signs of neurological involvement. In silico and cDNA sequencing studies showed that variant c.974dupG gives rise to skipping of exon 7. The expression of BSCL2-201 in fibroblasts was significantly higher in the index case than in the healthy child, although less than in the case with homozygous PELD due to c.985C>T variant. The expression of this transcript was approximately half in the healthy carrier parents of this patient. Conclusions: The c.974dupG variant leads to the skipping of exon 7 of the BSCL2 gene, and is responsible for a variant of Celia's encephalopathy, with variable phenotypic expression.</p>	

Ref.: Ms. No. NEGE-D-18-00135

March 14th, 2019

Prof. Georg Auburger
Editor-in-Chief
Neurogenetics

Dear Prof. Georg Auburger,

On behalf of my coauthors, please find attached the new version of the manuscript entitled "*Celia's encephalopathy and c.974dupG in BSCL2 gene: a hidden change in a known variant*" (NEGE-D-18-00135). We appreciate very much your nice comments about this manuscript.

We have tried to answer all the reviewers's comments and suggestions (in blue). We hope that this new version of our manuscript is suitable now for publication in your prestigious journal.

This contribution represents original work and has not been previously published or simultaneously submitted for publication elsewhere. I have read and have abided by the statement of ethical standards for manuscripts submitted to Neurogenetics

Thank you for your consideration of this manuscript.

Warm regards,

David Araújo-Vilar, MD, PhD
UETeM, Lab 3
Biomedical Research Institute (CIMUS)
University of Santiago de Compostela
Rua Barcelona 3
15707 Santiago de Compostela, Spain
E-mail: david.araujo@usc.es

"Celia's encephalopathy and c.974dupG in BSCL2 gene: a hidden change in a known variant" (NEGE-D-18-00135)

Reviewers' comments:

We first wish to thank both reviewers for their constructive remarks. We have revised the manuscript according to their valuable comments.

Reviewer #1: This manuscript provides further molecular genetic assessment of the rare syndrome of progressive childhood neurodegenerative disorder often associated with lipodystrophy (PELD aka Celia's encephalopathy). The authors have carefully studied the variant "c.974dupG" in BSCL2 (Berardinelli-Seip Congenital Lipodystrophy 2 gene) previously associated with this disease. The present study was based on the proximity of this variant to another specific variant, "c.985C>T", initially implicated in the disease and known to induce exon 7 skipping. The authors present the phenotype of two patients with lipodystrophy carrying the "c.974dupG" variant, one of them at least displaying a severe form of neuropathy. The analysis of patients' fibroblasts revealed that the c.974dupG variant indeed induces BSCL2-exon 7 skipping resulting in the same sequence alteration as for "c.985dupG" variant. The authors finally reviewed cases with the "c.974dupG" variant in BSCL2 who have been reported in literature. They conclude that the "c.974dupG" variant is responsible for PELD with variable phenotypic expression.

This paper reports interesting cases with a clinical phenotype clearly exposed. The demonstration of the "c.974dupG" variant in BSCL2 as responsible for exon 7 skipping, although very simple in principle, is particularly interesting. It reinforces the notion that the transcript which lacks exon 7 might play a specific role in neurodegeneration.

I have a few comments that might improve the manuscript:

1. Because the "c.974dupG" variant causes BSCL2-exon 7 skipping as does the "c.985C>T" variant in PELD, an extension of the review on the phenotype characteristics to all patients with a BSCL2-skipped exon 7 whatever the variant would be interesting. These could include patients with the c.985C>T variant and those with variants located in the flanking intronic splice sites of exon 7.

Answer: Thank for your suggestion. We have included in Discussion a summary of the main clinical features of classical phenotype of patients carrying the variant c.985C>T, and some comment about at least a variant located intronic splice site of exon 7 (in blue).

Page 11, line 305: "Briefly, patients with classic Celia's encephalopathy are normal at birth; by age 2 years these children show psychomotor delay, with both poor motor coordination and language and unsteady gait. As a rule, around 3 years old these patients showed a rapid psychomotor regression, with lost all language and showed severe cognitive impairment. By age 4 years, they have ataxic gait, tremor, dystonia, sleep disturbances and myoclonic epileptic seizures. Usually, before 6 years they have severe encephalopathy and progressive deterioration, leading to passed away before 8 [5]. In the same way, PELD patients show similar epileptic features and neuroimaging findings than case#1, particularly caudate atrophy and a marked decrease in glucose uptake in the parietal and occipital lobes [5,24]. On the other hand, expression of BSCL2-201 transcript in the index case of Celia's encephalopathy

[3] in non-neural tissues was increased, but the abnormal transcript was much more highly expressed in brain”.

2. Could the authors precise in the manuscript whether they are BSCL2 patients with neurological signs carrying a variant in another region of the gene ?

Answer: We are assuming that the reviewer is referring to subjects with type 2 congenital generalized lipodystrophy, because some specific variants in *BSCL2* gene are associated to motor neuron disease (Silver syndrome, distal hereditary motor neuropathy type VA). A comment about other biallelic variants in other exons of *BSCL2* related to neurological signs and generalized lipodystrophy has been included in the new version of the manuscript (in blue).

Page 12, line 351:” A review of other reported variants which could lead to the skipping exon 7 suggests that the variant c.864-2A>G (rs766061024, NM_001122955.3), originally reported as IVS6-2A>G [17], is especially interesting because is a splice acceptor variant (intron 6-7). This might lead to a cryptic splice site, although this never has not been studied. This variant was associated to congenital generalized lipodystrophy with mental retardation, but not with neurodegeneration [17]. Very recently, the biallelic variant c.1076dupC (p.Glu360*), located in exon 9 of the *BSCL2* gene, has been associated with congenital generalized lipodystrophy, myoclonic seizures, and progressive neurological degeneration [26].”

3. The increased expression of the altered transcript lacking exon 7 in the patients carrying the "c.974dupG" variant is not convincing as it is presented in the manuscript - in fibroblasts and in lymphocytes - although we can't exclude that the phenomenon occurs in brain.

Answer: We agree with the reviewer that the ideal scenario would have been to analyze the *BSCL2* transcript in brain tissues, however, unfortunately autopsy was not performed in patient #1. Expression of *BSCL2*-201 transcript in the index case of Celia's encephalopathy (ref. 5) in non-neural tissues was increased, but the abnormal transcript was much more highly expressed in brain.

4. A major concern is the variant nomenclature used in the manuscript. It is almost impossible to find the numbering in the numbering. Although some rules might have changed over the years (the authors can presently refer to the sequence variant nomenclature <http://varnomen.hgvs.org/recommendations/general/>), it is usually admitted that variants should be described at the most basic level, the DNA level, in relation to an accepted reference sequence. Descriptions at the RNA or protein level may be given in addition. This is particularly important in the case of *BSCL2* which encodes several protein isoforms. The seminal manuscript based the numbering on the 398 AA-isoform and a majority of manuscripts in literature followed it - probably to avoid confusion but also because it is still recognised as the canonical sequence in some databases. Nevertheless, without entering into this debate, the authors should use an unquestionable nomenclature (at the DNA level), the variant identification number (for instance, the "c.974dupG" variant id is rs749890533; the "c1015C>T" variant ID is rs137852974) and, a database allowing to choose the transcript and thus to find oneself in the numbering process. They could use Gnomad or alternatively modify their database (presently based on the 462 AA- isoform) to allow the switch between the transcripts.

Answer: The variants identification numbers (dbSNP) have now been added for all variants mentioned in the manuscript to avoid any kind of confusion (c.974dup: rs749890533; c.985C>T = rs587777606; c.757G>T = rs137852975; c.1015C>T = rs137852974; c.864-2A>G = rs766061024)

5. Figure 2 is not very informative and requires images from age-matched healthy controls for comparison with patients and arrows or informations to point the regions of interest.

Answer: We have included an age-matched healthy control for 18F-FDG PET, and also indicated the affected brain areas by arrows. In the case of brain MRI of patient #1, we have indicated the affected areas by arrows and arrowhead.

6. Table 3 is almost unreadable.

Answer: Table 3 has now been modified to make it easily readable. Font size has been augmented and table has been oriented in a landscape mode.

7. Please remove the sentence "Conditions and primers available upon request" for the molecular analysis of *BSCL2* exons because these were presented in the seminal paper on *BSCL2*.

Answer: The primers we used for *BSCL2* sequencing are not those which were presented in the seminal paper on *BSCL2*, instead they were designed by our group and their sequences are available upon request.

Reviewer #2: This is a very interesting manuscript reporting the functional consequences of the c.974dupG variant of *BSCL2* and bringing new data to the understanding of the genotype - phenotype correlations.

The discussion is sound.

I have a few comments:

- abstract: replace "mental retardation" by "intellectual deciciency"

Answer: The words "mental retardation" have now been replaced by "intellectual deficiency" as suggested by the reviewer.

- there are probably to much figures/tables. I suggest keeping only those that illustrate the findings and place the others as supplementary material. To my opinion the most important are figure 3 to 5.

Answer: Figures 1 and 2 have been moved to electronic supplementary material.

- The authors should explain in the introduction or in the discussion the number and types of transcripts of *BSCL2* and their relative expressions levels in normal individuals

Answer: Expression levels of *BSCL2* transcripts have been included in the introduction following Reviewer's suggestion.

Page 3, line 88: "This gene mainly encodes three seipin isoforms, 462 (*BSCL2*-203, ENST00000360796.9; CCDS44627), 398 (*BSCL2*-205/207/210, ENST00000403550.5; ENST00000407022.7; ENST00000421906.5; CCDS8031), and 287 (*BSCL2*-201, ENST00000278893.11; CCDS55769) amino acids long, respectively [2]. In humans, this *BSCL2*-203 is expressed primarily in the brain (78.9%), whereas *BSCL2*-205/207/210 expression is similar to *BSCL2*-203 in extraneural tissues and the peripheral nervous system (~50%), and *BSCL2*-201 expression is low in all tissues (<1%) [3]. The 462 and 398 amino acids isoforms have 2 cytoplasmic amino and carboxy terminal domains, one intraluminal loop, and two transmembrane domains [4]."

- The conclusion of the abstract and of the text are not clear and should be improved

Answer: We have tried to improve the conclusions in the new version of the manuscript.

[Click here to view linked References](#)

Celia's encephalopathy and c.974dupG in *BSCL2* gene: a hidden change in a known variant

Sofía Sánchez-Iglesias¹ (ORCID: 0000-0003-3887-0573), Melissa Crocker², Mar O'Callaghan³ (ORCID: 0000-0002-1896-1622), Alejandra Darling³ (ORCID: 0000-0003-0344-5809), Angels García-Cazorla³ (ORCID: 0000-0001-9853-688X), Rosario Domingo-Jiménez⁴, Ana Castro⁵ (ORCID: 0000-0002-6314-4445), Antía Fernández-Pombo^{1,5} (ORCID: 0000-0002-1268-7538), Álvaro Ruibal^{6,7} (ORCID: 0000-0002-6001-547X), Pablo Aguiar^{6,7} (ORCID: 0000-0002-7322-2195), Miguel Garrido-Pumar^{6,7}, Antonio Rodríguez-Núñez⁸ (ORCID: 0000-0003-3414-2771), Julián Álvarez-Escudero⁹, Rebecca J. Brown¹⁰ (ORCID: 0000-0002-2589-7382), David Araujo-Vilar^{1,5,*} (ORCID: 0000-0003-2852-7851)

Institutions

1. Thyroid and Metabolic Diseases Unit, Biomedical Research Institute (CIMUS)-IDIS, School of Medicine, Universidade de Santiago de Compostela, Spain.
2. Boston Children's Hospital, Harvard University, MA, USA
3. Servicio de Neurología, Hospital Sant Joan de Déu, Barcelona, Spain
4. Section of Neuropediatrics, Division of Pediatrics, Hospital Clínico Universitario Virgen de la Arrixaca-IMIB Arrixaca, Murcia, Spain
5. Division of Endocrinology and Nutrition, Hospital Clínico Universitario de Santiago de Compostela, Spain
6. Division of Nuclear Medicine, Hospital Clínico Universitario de Santiago de Compostela, Santiago de Compostela, Spain
7. Molecular Imaging and Medical Physics. Universidade de Santiago de Compostela. IDIS, Spain
8. Pediatric Intensive Care Unit, Pediatric Area, Hospital Clínico Universitario de Santiago de Compostela, Spain
9. Anesthesia and Reanimation Department, Hospital Clínico Universitario de Santiago de Compostela, Spain.
10. National Institute of Diabetes and Digestive and Kidney Diseases, National Institutes of Health, Bethesda, MD, USA

*Corresponding author

Address for correspondence:

David Araujo-Vilar, MD PhD
U.E.T.eM. CIMUS.
Avda. de Barcelona 3
University of Santiago de Compostela
15707 Santiago de Compostela, Spain.
Phone: +34 881815426, Fax: +34 88115403, E-mail: david.araujo@usc.es

Running title: Celia's encephalopathy and c.974dupG in *BSCL2*

Word count: Abstract: 291, Text: 3948

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

We are indebted to the patients and their parents for their collaboration in this study. This work was supported by the Instituto de Salud Carlos III and the European Regional Development Fund, FEDER (grants number PI10/02873 and PI13/00314), by the Consellería de Industria, Xunta de Galicia (grants number 10PXIB208013PR and ED341b 2017/19), and by Fundación Mutua Madrileña (Call 2015). S.S-I was awarded a Research Fellowship, granted by the Asociación Española de Familiares y Afectados de Lipodistrofias (AELIP). Evaluation of Case 2 was supported by the intramural research program of the National Institute of Diabetes and Digestive and Kidney Diseases. [Control 18F-FDG PET brain of subject at 7 years of age was a courtesy of A. Niñerola-Baizán and X. Setoain from Hospital Clínic Barcelona.](#)

ABSTRACT

Celia's encephalopathy (Progressive Encephalopathy with/without Lipodystrophy, PELD) is a childhood neurodegenerative disorder with a fatal prognosis before the age of 10, due to the variant c.985C>T in the *BSCL2* gene that causes a cryptic splicing site leading to skipping of exon 7. For years, different authors have reported cases of congenital generalized lipodystrophy due to the variant c.974dupG in *BSCL2* associated with neurological manifestations of variable severity, although some of them clearly superimposable to PELD. **Aim:** To identify the molecular mechanisms responsible for these neurological alterations in two patients with c.974dupG. **Subjects and Methods:** Clinical characterization, biochemistry and neuroimaging studies of two girls carrying this variant. *In silico* analysis, PCR amplification and *BSCL2* cDNA sequencing. *BSCL2*-201 transcript expression, which lacks exon 7, by qPCR in fibroblasts from the index case, from a healthy child as a control and from two patients with PELD, and in leukocytes from the index case and her parents. **Results:** One of the children presented with a severe encephalopathy including a picture of [intellectual deficiency](#), severe language impairment, myoclonic epilepsy and lipodystrophy as described in PELD, dying at 9 years and 9 months of age. The other 2-year-old patient showed incipient signs of neurological involvement. *In silico* and cDNA sequencing studies showed that variant c.974dupG gives rise to skipping of exon 7. The expression of *BSCL2*-201 in fibroblasts was significantly higher in the index case than in the healthy child, although less than in the case with homozygous PELD due to c.985C>T variant. The expression of this transcript was approximately half in the healthy carrier parents of this patient. **Conclusions:** The c.974dupG variant [leads to the skipping of exon 7 of the *BSCL2* gene, and is](#) responsible for a variant of Celia's encephalopathy, with variable phenotypic expression.

KEYWORDS: *BSCL2*, PELD, neurodegeneration, congenital generalized lipodystrophy, cryptic splicing.

INTRODUCTION

Seipin is a resident protein of the endoplasmic reticulum (ER), encoded by the *BSCL2* gene (NM_001122955.3), which is directly involved in the biogenesis of lipid droplets [1]. This gene mainly encodes three seipin isoforms, 462 (*BSCL2-203*, ENST00000360796.9; CCDS44627), 398 (*BSCL2-205/207/210*, ENST00000403550.5; ENST00000407022.7; ENST00000421906.5; CCDS8031), and 287 (*BSCL2-201*, ENST00000278893.11; CCDS55769) amino acids long, respectively [2]. In humans, *BSCL2-203* is expressed primarily in the brain (78.9%), whereas *BSCL2-205/207/210* expression is similar to *BSCL2-203* in extraneural tissues and the peripheral nervous system ($\approx 50\%$), and *BSCL2-201* expression is low in all tissues ($<1\%$) [3]. The 462 and 398 amino acids isoforms have 2 cytoplasmic amino and carboxy terminal domains, one intraluminal loop, and two transmembrane domains [4].

Celia's encephalopathy or PELD (Progressive Encephalopathy with/without Lipodystrophy, MIM: # 615924) [5] is a very rare pediatric neurodegenerative disorder with a fatal prognosis caused by the variant c.985C>T ([rs587777606](#)) in the *BSCL2* gene in homozygosis or compound heterozygosis. This variant results in skipping of exon 7 due to the appearance of a canonical branch site in this exon [5]. The intronization of exon 7 leads to the overexpression of the 287 amino acid seipin isoform (ENST00000278893.11) in the brain of these patients [3, 5]. This isoform, which lacks the second transmembrane domain and the carboxy-terminal cytoplasmic end, forms macroaggregates in neurons leading to ER stress and nuclear accumulation, and finally to apoptosis, which is the mechanism responsible for the neurological deterioration in these patients [6].

Patients with PELD have a psychomotor delay that appears after 2 years of age. After age three to four years they develop a process of neurological deterioration associated with refractory or drug-resistant myoclonic epilepsy, leading to death before age 9. Compound heterozygous patients, in addition to the neurodegenerative picture, have congenital generalized lipodystrophy (CGL, also named type 2 Berardinelli-Seip syndrome) associated with the metabolic and hepatic complications characteristic of this disorder [5, 7, 8]. To date, only 8 cases of PELD have been reported worldwide, 6 in Spain [5], one in Iran [9] and another in Brazil [Dr. L. Reis, personal communication], of which only 2 remain alive.

For years, more than 40 pathogenic variants have been reported in the *BSCL2* gene (<https://databases.lovd.nl/shared/genes/BSCL2>), which may lead to congenital generalized lipodystrophy (recessive disorder, MIM: #269700) [10] or to a upper and/or lower motor neuron disease (dominant disorder) [11, 12]. Strikingly, and unlike other subtypes of Berardinelli-Seip syndrome caused by variants in other genes (*AGPAT2*, MIM: # 608594; *CAV1*, MIM: #612526; *PTRF*, MIM: #613327) [13-15], the lipodystrophy due to *BSCL2* variants is usually associated with a certain degree of intellectual disability [16].

In 2003, the c.974dupG variant in *BSCL2* ([rs749890533](#), previously called c.1126insG (p.G271fsX283)) [17] was reported for the first time as responsible for CGL with mental retardation in a 9 years old girl. Theoretically, this variant would result in p.(Ile326HisfsTer12) in seipin. Subsequently, this same variant, referred to as c.783insG, was reported in two Chinese patients [18, 19]. One of these patients, aged 28 years, presented with dystonia in addition to CGL [18]; the other, at approximately 2 years of age, had generalized lipodystrophy with metabolic derangements without reported neurologic signs or symptoms [19].

More recently, Opri et al. (2016) [20] reported three cases of lethal epileptic encephalopathy associated with CGL caused by c.974dupG in *BSCL2* ([rs749890533](#), in the original referred to as c.782_783dupG). These patients had a neurological picture very similar to Celia's encephalopathy, with death occurring between 8 and 12 years of age [20].

In this study, we present two female patients, one dead at 9 years and 9 months of age, harboring the c.974dupG *BSCL2* biallelic variant, and other one aged 2, carrying the *BSCL2* variants c.[974dupG];[1015C>T] ([rs749890533](#); [rs137852974](#)). The first patient had a severe progressive encephalopathy with generalized lipodystrophy, superimposable with PELD, while the second one, at present, beside generalized lipodystrophy, shows a degree of speech delay and some tensing movements before sleep that appear to be self-soothing behaviors. We unveil in this work the molecular mechanisms responsible for this neurological disorder.

SUBJECTS AND METHODS

The regional IRBs approved this study, which was conducted according to the ethical guidelines of the Helsinki Declaration. The patients' parents gave informed written consent for the subjects' participation in the study and for the publication of clinical, imaging and genetic information.

Case reports

Case #1 (index case). The child is a girl born to non-consanguineous Caucasian parents after an uneventful pregnancy and delivery at 38 weeks of gestation (birth weight: 2855 gr (-0.34 SD); length: 48 cm (-0.41 SD)). During the first days after birth she was hyporeactive presenting feeding difficulties. During the second week of life failure to thrive, a lipodystrophic phenotype, hepatomegaly and hypertriglyceridemia (22.6 mmol/L) were noticed. Hepatomegaly and hypertriglyceridemia were normalized with diet at the age of 10-11 months. The family pointed out that she was always hyporeactive and somnolent. Despite this, early developmental milestones were achieved appropriately until 18 months of age. She sat by herself by 7-8 months, she walked at 14 months and started developing language by 18 months. By age 2 language delay was evident, while social and communication abilities were preserved. Language development evolved positively, she learnt some children's song and developed symbolic play by age 5. Since age 6 she showed motor and language regression. By age 7 she lost the ability to speak properly and gait became unsteady with frequent falls. Also stereotyped movements appeared, including orolingual dystonia with tongue protrusion. Motor regression continued in childhood, with progressive motor, language and cognitive deterioration. By age 8 she had lost the ability to walk and seat independently. Also, signs of dysphagia with frequent chokes were present at this time. After age 9 the disease progression was rapid over a few months presenting myoclonus and a prolonged generalized tonic clonic seizure. Electroencephalogram was abnormal showing frequent multifocal epileptiform anomalies. At this time valproate was initiated controlling the myoclonic seizures only partially.

At the age of 9 she presented severe cognitive impairment, myoclonic epilepsy, and absence of language abilities; she was wheelchair bounded and totally dependent for all the daily life activities. The dysphagia contributed to the severe deterioration of her nutritional status at that time and a nasogastric tube for feeding was required. Finally, the patient died at the age of 9 years and 9 months.

On physical examination, she always had marked generalized lipoatrophy (Figure S1, [electronic supplementary material](#)), with minimal fat in the palms and soles, without phlebomegaly, acanthosis nigricans or muscular hypertrophy. The face was triangular without coarse features. Hepatomegaly was not present. She had severe axial hypotonia with no independent sedestation and gait. Pyramidal signs were present, showing hyperreflexia in upper and lower limbs, lower limb spasticity, lower limb distal retraction and extensor plantar reflex.

By age 2 the diagnosis of type 2 Berardinelli-Seip syndrome (c.974dupG, p.(Ile326HisfsTer12) in *BSCL2* in homozygosis, [rs749890533](#)) was confirmed. The analytical parameters during the first year were normal, except for hypertriglyceridemia, and leptinemia which was always low (<0.1 ng/mL). The anthropometric and analytical data are shown in Table 1.

At age 9 electrophysiological studies were abnormal, showing in the electroencephalography a diffuse distribution of monomorphic brain activity formed by theta and delta waves and low voltage beta rhythm, associated with frequent multifocal epileptiform anomalies consisting of acute waves and irregular spike-and-wave complexes of medium and high amplitude. Electromyography and nerve conduction studies showed signs of an axonal-type sensorimotor neuropathy mainly in lower limbs.

Neuroimaging studies were obtained at the age of 7.8 and 9 years. At 7.8 years of life, the brain MRI-PET study showed bilateral caudate volume loss and a marked glucose hypometabolism in parietal and occipital lobes of both hemispheres, while the other structures included in the study were in within normal parameters (Figure S2A, [electronic supplementary material](#)). By age 9 an MRI was obtained showing a progression of the volume loss of the structures of both striated regions, specially the caudate nucleus. Moreover, globus pallidus hypointensity was observed in the susceptibility-weighted image sequence (Figure S2B, [electronic supplementary material](#)).

Case #2. The patient is a 2 year 6 month old girl who carried the variants c.[974dupG];[1015C>T] ([rs749890533](#); [rs137852974](#)) in *BSCL2* gene. She was the product of a full-term, uncomplicated pregnancy. She presented to medical attention at age 6 weeks due to failure-to-thrive, with a decrease in weight-for-length centile from approximately the 10th centile in the first week of life, to <1st centile. During hospitalization at age 6 weeks, she was noted to have hypertriglyceridemia (>28.25 mmol/L), triangular facies, and generalized lack of adipose tissue, leading to the diagnosis

of congenital generalized lipodystrophy. At age 6 months, she was doing well on high-calorie MCT oil based formula, with normal motor, social, and language development. Physical exam showed mild acanthosis nigricans and generalized absence of subcutaneous fat. Laboratory findings included high triglycerides (3.68 mmol/L), low HDL-c (0.39 mmol/L), high insulin (431 pmol/L) with normal hemoglobin A1c (4.8%), and increased liver echogenicity on ultrasound consistent with steatosis. She was initiated on metreleptin, 0.07 mg/kg per day.

At 7-8 months of age she was noted to have episodes of stiffening that would only occur while she was lying on her stomach, especially before falling asleep. She would tense her pelvis, legs and arms, but the activity was suppressible. These were thought to be self-soothing behaviors. By age 2 she was also identified to have some mild speech delay. [The anthropometric and analytical data are shown in Table 2.](#)

Genetic studies

For the variant analyses, genomic DNA was isolated from peripheral leukocytes using standard procedures [21]. *BSCL2* exons 1-11, and the surrounding intronic sequences from the subjects, were PCR-amplified and sequenced. PCR conditions and primer sequences are available upon request.

Splicing analysis of the *BSCL2* c.974dupG variant

The following *in silico* programs were used to predict the effect of the variants on splicing: Human Splice Finder (HSF, version 3.1, <http://www.umd.be/HSF3/>), NetGene2 (version 2.4, <http://www.cbs.dtu.dk/services/NetGene2/>), NNSplice (version 0.9, http://www.fruitfly.org/seq_tools/splice.html), Alternative Splice Site Predictor (ASSP, <http://wangcomputing.com/assp/>), and MutPred splice (version 1.3.2, <http://www.mutdb.org/mutpredsplice/submit.htm>). The latter was used to identify single base substitutions in exonic regions that disrupt pre-mRNA. They were accessed individually and the analyses were done using default settings.

***BSCL2* expression studies**

Total RNA was extracted from leukocytes and primary fibroblasts and reverse-transcribed as previously reported [22]. *BSCL2* cDNA was amplified with primers designed with the Primer3Plus

software (<http://www.bioinformatics.nl/cgi-bin/primer3plus/primer3plus.cgi>) (forward: 5'-CAGATGCTGGACACACTGGT-3', reverse: 5'-ATCACTGGCCTCAGGCTCTA-3'). PCR conditions are available upon request. Amplification fragments obtained were separated out by low-melting agarose gel electrophoresis (1%). The resulting bands were excised from agarose gel, and cDNA was extracted using the Qiaex II gel extraction kit (Qiagen, Chatsworth, CA, USA). cDNA was then amplified with the same primers and conditions as used for the first PCR; fragments were separated by agarose gel electrophoresis and directly sequenced.

Expression of *BSCL2* mRNA was quantified in a LightCycler 2.0 (Roche Diagnostics, Sant Cugat del Vallès, Spain) using specific probes and oligonucleotide primers designed by the Universal ProbeLibrary (Roche Diagnostics). Specific designed primers and probe were used for *BSCL2* spliced transcript. Details are available upon request. Results were normalized to the RNA polymerase II and 18S genes, using the $2^{-\Delta\Delta CT}$ method [23].

Skin biopsy and cell cultures

A small sample of skin from the abdominal area was obtained from the case 1 at age 7 years. A control skin sample was obtained from a 6-year-old normal boy during cryptorchidism surgery, in accordance with the ethical regulations of current Spanish legislation. Small pieces of tissue were rinsed with PBS and placed on a 60 mm dish (cat. 353004, Falcon™, Mississauga, ON, Canada) containing Dulbecco's modified Eagle's medium (DMEM, cat. D5796, Sigma-Aldrich, St. Louis, Missouri, USA) supplemented with 30% fetal bovine serum (FBS, cat. 10270, Gibco Life Technologies, Carlsbad, California, USA) and gentamicin 50 µg/ml (cat. G1397, Sigma-Aldrich), and incubated at 37 °C with 5% CO₂ in a Water-Jacket CO₂ incubator (Galaxy 170 S, Eppendorf New Brunswick, Hamburg, Germany). Fibroblasts were cultured with fresh medium, changed every three days, until a 70% confluent monolayer was obtained. Afterwards, they were trypsinized (cat. 12604-021, TrypLE™ Express, Gibco Life Technologies) and cultured on 100 mm dishes in DMEM containing 10% FBS and penicillin-streptomycin 1% (cat. 15140-122, Gibco Life Technologies).

Statistical analysis

Real-time PCR analyses were performed in duplicate. Statistical significance was determined using a non-parametric Kruskal-Wallis and Mann–Whitney tests. Data are presented as means \pm SD with the statistical significance set at $p < 0.05$. All statistical analyses were performed using SPSS for Mac (release 22.0; SPSS, Chicago, IL, USA).

RESULTS

The case #1 was homozygous for a guanine insertion in NM_001122955.3: c.974dupG, p.(Ile326HisfsTer12) ([rs749890533](#)) in *BSCL2* gene. Her parents were asymptomatic heterozygous carriers, while his brother was not carrier. The case #2 was a compound heterozygote for *BSCL2*: c.974dupG ([rs749890533](#)) in one allele and c.1015C>T ([rs137852974](#)), p.(Arg339Ter) in the other allele.

Given the great similarity between case #1 neurological disorder and Celia' encephalopathy, we hypothesized that the variant c.974dupG ([rs749890533](#)) could be given rise also to the skipping of exon 7 in *BSCL2*. As a first approach, we carried out different *in silico* analysis of this variant. Whereas we did not find any variations for splice sites (acceptor and donor values remain unchanged), HSF detected a potential alteration of the splicing in the branch point motif CCCCAG/GCCCCGA and in some auxiliary sequences, known as the exonic splicing enhancer (ESE) and the exonic splicing silencer (ESS) sites. These sequences, either enhance or repress splicing by modulating the assembly of the early-stage spliceosome complex. The variant c.974dupG ([rs749890533](#)) appears to alter an ESE site and to create a new ESS. All these disruptions might possibly compromise the splicing. Afterwards, in order to check these findings, we performed a *BSCL2* cDNA PCR including from exon 5 to exon 10, finding a 431 bp extra-band in case #1 (Figure 1A). Subsequently, this band was sequenced (Figure 1B), finding that the whole exon 7 disappeared, exactly as it happened with c.985C>T variant ([rs587777606](#)) [5].

In order to confirm these results, we measured the relative expression of *BSCL2*-201 transcript (which encodes the 287 amino acids seipin isoform and that lacks exon 7) in primary fibroblasts from case #1 and compared with control and Celia's encephalopathy primary fibroblasts. The expression of this transcript was 4 times higher than control, it was similar to that of the compound heterozygote patient for c.985C>T, and significantly lower than that quantified in the samples from the

homozygous patient with classical Celia's encephalopathy (Figure 2A). When we compared *BSCL2*-201 expression in white blood cells from case #1 with those from her heterozygous parents and normal brother, the results were as expected (Figure 2B): approximately half of expression in parents and around 20% in the wild type brother.

DISCUSSION

In this study we reported two cases of girls carrying the c.974dupG ([rs749890533](#)) variant in *BSCL2* gene, one homozygous and the other one a compound heterozygote. The first of these, who died before reaching 10 years of age, had, in addition to generalized lipodystrophy, a neurodegenerative picture starting at an early age, rapidly progressive after 8 years of age, associated with myoclonic epilepsy. The second, currently aged 2 years and 6 months, has generalized lipodystrophy and seems to be in the early stages of the neurological picture, although we cannot rule out the possible beneficial effect of metreleptin on the neurological clinic, as previously reported [24]. The first case corresponds clinically, electrophysiologically, and according to the neuroimaging tests with those reported in 2016 by Opri et al. (Table 3) [20], although the description in the original paper of the genotype of these patients corresponds to another *BSCL2* transcript, (NM_032667.6, which encodes the 398 amino acids seipin isoform) which may lead to confusion. The variant found by these authors was c.782_783dupG, which corresponds with c.974dupG ([rs749890533](#)) in NM_001122955.3 transcript, which encodes the 462 amino acids seipin isoform (<https://databases.lovd.nl/shared/genes/BSCL2>). Interestingly, this patient developed an axonal neuropathy, as it is described in other *BSCL2* related disorders [25], showing that *BSCL2* variants lead to different but overlapping phenotypes affecting both upper and lower neurons.

The molecular studies carried out both in leukocytes and fibroblasts of case #1 showed that the c.974dupG ([rs749890533](#)) variant in *BSCL2* gave rise to the skipping of exon 7 in this gene. This mechanism is identical to the one reported years ago by us in the case of Celia's encephalopathy, caused by the variant c.985C>T ([rs587777606](#)) in *BSCL2* [5]. The clinical features of Celia encephalopathy are superimposable to those of case #1, and also to those of case #2 in its initial stages. Briefly, patients with classic Celia's encephalopathy are normal at birth; by age 2 years these children show psychomotor delay, with both poor motor coordination and language and unsteady

gait. As a rule, around 3 years old these patients showed a rapid psychomotor regression, with lost all language and showed severe cognitive impairment. By age 4 years, they have ataxic gait, tremor, dystonia, sleep disturbances and myoclonic epileptic seizures. Usually, before 6 years they have severe encephalopathy and progressive deterioration, leading to passed away before 8 [5]. In the same way, PELD patients show similar epileptic features and neuroimaging findings than case #1, particularly caudate atrophy and a marked decrease in glucose uptake in the parietal and occipital lobes [5, 24]. On the other hand, expression of *BSCL2*-201 transcript in the index case of Celia's encephalopathy [5] in non-neural tissues was increased, but the abnormal transcript was much more highly expressed in brain.

In Celia's encephalopathy, the expression of the *BSCL2*-201 transcript (which lacks exon 7), which is hardly expressed in normal brain (<1%) [3, 5], was markedly elevated in the different areas of the brain analyzed in the index case of our initial study [5]. Although we did not have samples from the encephalon of case #1, we analyzed the expression of this transcript in fibroblasts from this patient, and compared it with that observed in fibroblasts from a healthy control child, being the expression of such a transcript 4 times higher than that of the control. On the other hand, and as expected, the expression of *BSCL2*-201 was lower in the leukocytes from the simple heterozygous healthy parents of case #1.

Taken together, the clinical, electrophysiological, imaging and molecular data of these patients, together with that previously reported in the literature (Table 3), suggest that the loss of exon 7 of *BSCL2* induced by the c.974dupG ([rs749890533](#)) variant is the cause of the neurodegenerative picture suffered by these patients. In previous studies of our group [5, 6], we showed that seipin encoded by this transcript tends to aggregate abnormally resulting in ER stress, intranuclear seipin inclusions and neuronal apoptosis [6].

The variant c.974dupG ([rs749890533](#)) had already been reported in 2003 [17] although with another notation (c.1126insG, p.(G271fsX283)). In this case, the patient (GC1100), aged 9 years, had mental retardation in addition to lipodystrophy and diabetes, but no reference was made to a neurodegenerative picture. It is noteworthy that in this case this variant was in simple heterozygosis and no other pathogenic variant was found in *BSCL2*. Later, Wu et al. (2009) [18] and Huang et al. (2010) [19] reported 2 cases of CLG associated with the c.975dupG variant (according to

<https://databases.lovd.nl/shared/variants/0000021148#00023833>), although in the original articles it was reported to as c.783insG. Theoretically this variant would originate the same change in seipin than c.974dupG, that is, p.(Ile326HisfsTer12). However, after a careful analysis of *BSCL2*-203 sequence (Figure 3), we found that the correct notation is c.974dupG, as the 975 position in the ENST00000360796.9 transcript corresponds to a cytosine. Furthermore, the HGVS notation prescribes that, like in this case where there is one guanine insertion among the seven guanines from 968 to 974 positions, the notation insertion must be referred to the last 3' guanine (3' rule). Strikingly, the study by Wu et al. (2009) [18] describes a 26-year-old man, compound heterozygote (c.[757G>T];[974dupG] or c.[565G>T];[783insG] in the original, [rs137852975](#); [rs749890533](#)), with generalized lipodystrophy and a picture of intellectual disability and generalized dystonia. The variant c.757G>T ([rs137852975](#), exon 5) would give rise to a premature stop codon, p.(Glu253Ter). On the other hand, Huang et al. (2010) [19] reported the case of a 1.8-year-old child carrying the same variant c.974dupG (c.783insG in the original) than Wu et al. [18] in homozygosity in *BSCL2*, with a clear CGL picture, but he did not show any intellectual impairment at that age. However, we do not know how the neurological evolution of this patient was over the years.

A review of other reported variants which could lead to the skipping exon 7 suggests that the variant c.864-2A>G ([rs766061024](#), NM_001122955.3), originally reported as IVS6-2A>G [17], is especially interesting because is a splice acceptor variant (intron 6-7). This might lead to a cryptic splice site, although this never has not been studied. This variant was associated to congenital generalized lipodystrophy with mental retardation, but not with neurodegeneration [17]. Very recently, the biallelic variant c.1076dupC (p.Glu360*), located in exon 9 of the *BSCL2* gene, has been associated with congenital generalized lipodystrophy, myoclonic seizures, and progressive neurological degeneration [26].

Supporting our hypothesis that the skipping of exon 7 is critical for explaining the neurological symptoms of these patients, recently, Poisson et al. (2018) [27] reported the case of a patient, who died at 28 years of age, and who during the first years was diagnosed with a regressive autism spectrum disorder, although at the age of 6 years he presented motor stereotypies and lower limbs hypertonia; from 16 to 23 years of age, the neurological picture was getting worse, and a clear frontal lobe syndrome appeared [27]. The brain MRI disclosed bilateral atrophy of the caudate nucleus.

Interestingly, the authors report no lipodystrophy or metabolic alterations in this patient. This patient was a carrier of the variants c.[985C>T];[1004A>C] in *BSCL2*. The first is the classic variant responsible for Celia's encephalopathy. The second variant (c.1004A>C) would theoretically give rise to the missense change p.(Gln335Pro), which according to PolyPhen-2 is possibly damaging (PolyPhen-2, score: 0.522), although it has never been reported as a cause of CGL (<https://databases.lovd.nl/shared/genes/BSCL2>). *In silico* analysis with MutPred splice software for c.1004A>C variant indicates a score of 0.84 predicting to be a splice affecting variant with high confident hypothesis ($p < 0.000001$), whereas HSF did not detect any significant splicing motif alteration. Based on *in silico* and RNA retrotranscription studies (although not direct sequencing), the authors concluded that the variant c.1004A>C also gives rise to the skipping of exon 7 in the *BSCL2* gene. The fact that this patient did not present with lipodystrophy could suggest that the variant c.1004A>C does not impair the lipid droplets biogenesis. On the other hand, the late appearance of neurodegenerative symptoms and long survival suggest that the splicing rate induced by c.1004A>C could be low. Our *in vitro* studies [6] showed that if the amount of wt seipin is sufficient (as in the simple heterozygotes), the aberrant seipin would be sequestered by the homo-oligomers of wt protein. According to all these data, we can speculate that the neurodegenerative process would be more or less aggressive depending on two factors, the rate of splicing induced by a particular variant in the exon 7, and of the presence or not of variants in the other allele which allow the translation of an abnormal seipin isoform with certain capability for kidnapping the 287 amino acids seipin.

In summary, certain variants in exon 7 of *BSCL2* gene originate splicing alterations that lead to the skipping of this exon and consequently to the excessive production of the 287 amino acids seipin isoform at a variable rate, either in homozygosis or in compound heterozygosis, generally leading to a lethal neurodegenerative condition, with special involvement of the striated nuclei, particularly the caudate. However, at present, we have not a clear explanation for the different neurological phenotype previously reported.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

REFERENCES

1. Wang, H., et al., *Seipin is required for converting nascent to mature lipid droplets*. *Elife*, 2016. **5**: p. e16582.
2. Cartwright, B.R. and J.M. Goodman, *Seipin: from human disease to molecular mechanism*. *J Lipid Res*, 2012. **53**(6): p. 1042-55.
3. Sanchez-Iglesias, S., et al., *Does Seipin Play a Role in Oxidative Stress Protection and Peroxisome Biogenesis? New Insights from Human Brain Autopsies*. *Neuroscience*, 2019. **396**: p. 119-137.
4. Lundin, C., et al., *Membrane topology of the human seipin protein*. *FEBS Lett*, 2006. **580**(9): p. 2281-4.
5. Guillen-Navarro, E., et al., *A new seipin-associated neurodegenerative syndrome*. *J Med Genet*, 2013. **50**(6): p. 401-9.
6. Ruiz-Riquelme, A., et al., *Larger aggregates of mutant seipin in Celia's Encephalopathy, a new protein misfolding neurodegenerative disease*. *Neurobiol Dis*, 2015. **83**: p. 44-53.
7. Brown, R.J., et al., *The Diagnosis and Management of Lipodystrophy Syndromes: A Multi-Society Practice Guideline*. *J Clin Endocrinol Metab*, 2016. **101**(12): p. 4500-4511.
8. Araujo-Vilar, D. and F. Santini, *Diagnosis and treatment of lipodystrophy: a step-by-step approach*. *J Endocrinol Invest*, 2018.
9. Alaei, M.R., et al., *Whole Exome Sequencing Reveals a BSCL2 Mutation Causing Progressive Encephalopathy with Lipodystrophy (PELD) in an Iranian Pediatric Patient*. *Iran Biomed J*, 2016. **20**(5): p. 295-301.
10. Magre, J., et al., *Identification of the gene altered in Berardinelli-Seip congenital lipodystrophy on chromosome 11q13*. *Nat Genet*, 2001. **28**(4): p. 365-70.
11. Auer-Grumbach, M., et al., *Phenotypes of the N88S Berardinelli-Seip congenital lipodystrophy 2 mutation*. *Ann Neurol*, 2005. **57**(3): p. 415-24.
12. Irobi, J., et al., *The phenotype of motor neuropathies associated with BSCL2 mutations is broader than Silver syndrome and distal HMN type V*. *Brain*, 2004. **127**(Pt 9): p. 2124-30.
13. Agarwal, A.K., et al., *AGPAT2 is mutated in congenital generalized lipodystrophy linked to chromosome 9q34*. *Nat Genet*, 2002. **31**(1): p. 21-3.
14. Kim, C.A., et al., *Association of a homozygous nonsense caveolin-1 mutation with Berardinelli-Seip congenital lipodystrophy*. *J Clin Endocrinol Metab*, 2008. **93**(4): p. 1129-34.
15. Hayashi, Y.K., et al., *Human PTRF mutations cause secondary deficiency of caveolins resulting in muscular dystrophy with generalized lipodystrophy*. *J Clin Invest*, 2009. **119**(9): p. 2623-33.
16. Van Maldergem, L., et al., *Genotype-phenotype relationships in Berardinelli-Seip congenital lipodystrophy*. *J Med Genet*, 2002. **39**(10): p. 722-33.
17. Agarwal, A.K., et al., *Phenotypic and genetic heterogeneity in congenital generalized lipodystrophy*. *J Clin Endocrinol Metab*, 2003. **88**(10): p. 4840-7.
18. Wu, Y.R., et al., *Complementary mutations in seipin gene in a patient with Berardinelli-Seip congenital lipodystrophy and dystonia: phenotype variability suggests multiple roles of seipin gene*. *J Neurol Neurosurg Psychiatry*, 2009. **80**(10): p. 1180-1.
19. Huang, H.H., et al., *A Taiwanese boy with congenital generalized lipodystrophy caused by homozygous Ile262fs mutation in the BSCL2 gene*. *Kaohsiung J Med Sci*, 2010. **26**(11): p. 615-20.
20. Opri, R., et al., *Progressive Myoclonus Epilepsy in Congenital Generalized Lipodystrophy type 2: Report of 3 cases and literature review*. *Seizure*, 2016. **42**: p. 1-6.
21. Sambrook, J. and D.W. Russell, *Molecular cloning : a laboratory manual*. 3rd ed. 2001, Cold Spring Harbor, N.Y.: Cold Spring Harbor Laboratory Press.
22. Victoria, B., et al., *Reduced adipogenic gene expression in fibroblasts from a patient with type 2 congenital generalized lipodystrophy*. *Diabet Med*, 2010. **27**(10): p. 1178-87.
23. Livak, K.J. and T.D. Schmittgen, *Analysis of relative gene expression data using real-time quantitative PCR and the 2(-Delta Delta C(T)) Method*. *Methods*, 2001. **25**(4): p. 402-8.

24. Araujo-Vilar, D., et al., *Association of metreleptin treatment and dietary intervention with neurological outcomes in Celia's encephalopathy*. Eur J Hum Genet, 2018. **26**(3): p. 396-406.
25. Choi, B.O., et al., *Clinical and histopathological study of Charcot-Marie-Tooth neuropathy with a novel S90W mutation in BSCL2*. Neurogenetics, 2013. **14**(1): p. 35-42.
26. Serino, D., et al., *Berardinelli-Seip syndrome and progressive myoclonus epilepsy*. Epileptic Disord, 2019. **21**(1): p. 117-121.
27. Poisson, A., et al., *Regressive Autism Spectrum Disorder Expands the Phenotype of BSCL2/Seipin-Associated Neurodegeneration*. Biol Psychiatry, 2018. **S0006-3223**(18): p. 31524-31525.

TABLES

Table 1. Anthropometric and analytical data of case #1.

Age (y)	4	7	8	9
Weight (kg, P)	15.7 (P.25)	N.D.	18.9 (P.3)	20 (P.3)
Height (cm)	103 (P.75)	N.D.	124 (P.25)	130 (P.30)
Total fat (%)	N.D.	N.D.	12.8	N.D.
FFM (%)	N.D.	N.D.	80	N.D.
Tricipital S. (mm)	N.D.	N.D.	2	N.D.
Bicipital S. (mm)	N.D.	N.D.	2	N.D.
Subscapular S. (mm)	N.D.	N.D.	3	N.D.
Suprailiac S. (mm)	N.D.	N.D.	4	N.D.
Thigh S. (mm)	N.D.	N.D.	2	N.D.
Calf S. (mm)	N.D.	N.D.	2	N.D.
Glucose (mmol/L)	4.6	5.2	4.3	3.9
A1c (%)	4.8	N.D.	4.7	4.1
Creatinine (µmol/L)	40.7	59.5	30	46
Total cholesterol (mmol/L)	4.40	N.D.	5.31	5.51
LDL-cholesterol (mmol/L)	2.93	N.D.	3.86	N.D.
HDL-cholesterol (mmol/L)	0.88	N.D.	1.19	N.D.
Triglycerides (mmol/L)	1.28	N.D.	0.57	0.6
Insulin (mIU/L)	N.D.	N.D.	9.2	N.D.
Leptin (ng/mL)	N.D.	N.D.	<1.0	N.D.
AST (IU/L)	25	38	16	20
ALT (IU/L)	21	114	28	27
GGT (IU/L)	N.D.	31	22	33
CK (IU/L)	N.D.	N.D.	70	38
TSH (mUI/L)	N.D.	2.78	2.84	1.7

P: Percentile; N.D.: Not determined

Table 2. Anthropometric and analytical data of case #2.

Age (y)	6 months	13 months	24 months	30 months
Weight (kg, P)	6.83 (P.27)	8.2 (P.5)	11.1 (P.24)	12.5 (P.35)
Height (cm, P)	71.8 (P.>95)	78.8 (P.92)	89.6 (P.84)	94.7 (P.80)
Glucose (mmol/L)	4.2	4.7	4.4	4.3
A1c (%)	4.8	4.8	4.8	5
Creatinine (μ mol/L)	17.7	13.3	18.6	20.3
Total cholesterol (mmol/L)	4.01	3.83	2.59	2.97
LDL-cholesterol (mmol/L)	1.93	2.46	1.6	1.91
HDL-cholesterol (mmol/L)	0.39	0.67	0.78	0.9
Triglycerides (mmol/L)	3.68	1.54	0.43	0.35
Insulin (mIU/L)	62.1	7.3	5.7	1.6
AST (IU/L)	39	37	36	38
ALT (IU/L)	74	39	21	18

P: Percentile

Table 3. Clinical features of patients carrying the c.974dupG variant in *BSCL2* gene

Patient	Genotype	Intellectual deficiency (age)	Language delay	Myoclonus (age)	Dystonia (age)	Seizures (age)	Gait ataxia (age)	Abnormal behavior (age)	Severe encephalopathy (age)	Lip
Case #1	Hmzg	Yes (3)	Yes (2)	Yes (6)	Yes (7)	Yes (7)	Yes (7.8)	Yes (7.8)	Yes (9)	
Case #2	Comp Htzg	No	Yes (2)	No	No	No	No	Yes (0.7)	No	
Opri et al. 2016 [20] case #2	Hmzg	Yes (4)	N.R.	Yes (4)	N.R.	Yes (4)	Yes (6)	N.R.	Yes (7.5)	
Opri et al. 2016 [20] case #3	Hmzg	Yes (early)	N.R.	Yes (5)	N.R.	Yes (5)	Yes (10)	N.R.	Yes (10)	
Huang et al. 2010 [19]	Hmzg	No	N.R.	N.R.	N.R.	N.R.	N.R.	N.R.	N.R.	
Opri et al. 2016 [20] case #1	Comp Htzg (fs stop codon)	Yes (?)	Yes (1)	Yes (1)	Yes (1)	Yes (1)	Yes (5)	N.R.	Yes (7)	
Wu et al. 2009 [18]	Comp Htzg (stop codon)	Yes (?)	Yes (?)	No	Yes (?)	No	Yes (?)	Yes (?)	No	

Patient	Genotype	Intellectual deficiency (age)	Language delay	Myoclonus (age)	Dystonia (age)	Seizures (age)	Gait ataxia (age)	Abnormal behavior (age)	Severe encephalopathy (age)	Lip
Poisson et al. 2018 [27]	Comp Htzg (missense)	Yes (4-5)	Yes (3,5)	N.R.	Yes (16)	N.R.	Yes (16)	Yes (3)	Yes (23)	
Agarwal et al. 2003 [17]	Simple Htzg	Yes (?)	N.R.	N.R.	N.R.	N.R.	N.R.	N.R.	N.R.	

N.R.: Not reported

Figure legends

Figure 1. A. Results of the amplification of a 573 bp region of cDNA from leukocytes from the index case and different subjects. Samples from the 974dupG index case and 985C>T PELD index case show the presence of an additional 431 base pair-long band. **B.** Sequencing of the 431 base pair band showed complete skipping of exon 7.

Figure 2. A. Relative expression of *BSCL2*-201 transcript in fibroblasts from a control children, a homozygous PELD patient (c.985C>T), a compound heterozygous patient (c.[985C>T];[509_5013del] and case #1 (c.974dupG). *: p<0.05 compared with control; #: p<0.05 compared with homozygous PELD patient. **B.** Relative expression of *BSCL2*-201 transcript in leukocytes from case #1, her mother (simple heterozygous), her father (simple heterozygous) and brother (wt).

Figure 3. *BSCL2*-203 transcript sequence surrounding the c.974dupG (purple shading) and c.985C>T (red shading) variants, and the incorrectly annotated c.975dupG variant (grey shading).

A

B

Figure 2

A

B

Figure 3

BSCL2-203 (ENST00000360796.9)

Table 1. Anthropometric and analytical data of case #1.

Age (y)	4	7	8	9
Weight (kg, P)	15.7 (P.25)	N.D.	18.9 (P.3)	20 (P.3)
Height (cm)	103 (P.75)	N.D.	124 (P.25)	130 (P.30)
Total fat (%)	N.D.	N.D.	12.8	N.D.
FFM (%)	N.D.	N.D.	80	N.D.
Tricipital S. (mm)	N.D.	N.D.	2	N.D.
Bicipital S. (mm)	N.D.	N.D.	2	N.D.
Subscapular S. (mm)	N.D.	N.D.	3	N.D.
Suprailiac S. (mm)	N.D.	N.D.	4	N.D.
Thigh S. (mm)	N.D.	N.D.	2	N.D.
Calf S. (mm)	N.D.	N.D.	2	N.D.
Glucose (mmol/L)	4.6	5.2	4.3	3.9
A1c (%)	4.8	N.D.	4.7	4.1
Creatinine (μ mol/L)	40.7	59.5	30	46
Total cholesterol (mmol/L)	4.40	N.D.	5.31	5.51
LDL-cholesterol (mmol/L)	2.93	N.D.	3.86	N.D.
HDL-cholesterol (mmol/L)	0.88	N.D.	1.19	N.D.
Triglycerides (mmol/L)	1.28	N.D.	0.57	0.6
Insulin (mIU/L)	N.D.	N.D.	9.2	N.D.
Leptin (ng/mL)	N.D.	N.D.	<1.0	N.D.
AST (IU/L)	25	38	16	20
ALT (IU/L)	21	114	28	27
GGT (IU/L)	N.D.	31	22	33
CK (IU/L)	N.D.	N.D.	70	38
TSH (mUI/L)	N.D.	2.78	2.84	1.7

P: Percentile; N.D.: Not determined

Table 2. Anthropometric and analytical data of case #2.

Age (y)	6 months	13 months	24 months	30 months
Weight (kg, P)	6.83 (P.27)	8.2 (P.5)	11.1 (P.24)	12.5 (P.35)
Height (cm, P)	71.8 (P.>95)	78.8 (P.92)	89.6 (P.84)	94.7 (P.80)
Glucose (mmol/L)	4.2	4.7	4.4	4.3
A1c (%)	4.8	4.8	4.8	5
Creatinine (μ mol/L)	17.7	13.3	18.6	20.3
Total cholesterol (mmol/L)	4.01	3.83	2.59	2.97
LDL-cholesterol (mmol/L)	1.93	2.46	1.6	1.91
HDL-cholesterol (mmol/L)	0.39	0.67	0.78	0.9
Triglycerides (mmol/L)	3.68	1.54	0.43	0.35
Insulin (mIU/L)	62.1	7.3	5.7	1.6
AST (IU/L)	39	37	36	38
ALT (IU/L)	74	39	21	18

P: Percentile

Table 3. Clinical features of patients carrying the c.974dupG variant in *BSCL2* gene

Patient	Genotype	Intellectual deficiency (age)	Language delay	Myoclonus (age)	Dystonia (age)	Seizures (age)	Gait ataxia (age)	Abnormal behavior (age)	Severe encephalopathy (age)	Lipodystrophy (age)	Hypertriglyceridemia (age)	Hepatomegaly (age)	Exitus (age)
Case #1	Hmzg	Yes (3)	Yes (2)	Yes (6)	Yes (7)	Yes (7)	Yes (7.8)	Yes (7.8)	Yes (9)	Yes (birth)	Yes (birth)	Yes (birth)	Yes (9.8)
Case #2	Comp Htzg	No	Yes (2)	No	No	No	No	Yes (0.7)	No	Yes (birth)	Yes (birth)	Yes (birth)	No
Opri et al. 2016 [20] case #2	Hmzg	Yes (4)	N.R.	Yes (4)	N.R.	Yes (4)	Yes (6)	N.R.	Yes (7.5)	Yes (birth)	Yes (birth)	Yes (3)	Yes (7.8)
Opri et al. 2016 [20] case #3	Hmzg	Yes (early)	N.R.	Yes (5)	N.R.	Yes (5)	Yes (10)	N.R.	Yes (10)	Yes (birth)	Yes (birth)	N.R.	Yes (11)
Huang et al. 2010 [19]	Hmzg	No	N.R.	N.R.	N.R.	N.R.	N.R.	N.R.	N.R.	Yes (birth)	Yes (birth)	Yes (birth)	No (1.8)
Opri et al. 2016 [20] case #1	Comp Htzg (fs stop codon)	Yes (?)	Yes (1)	Yes (1)	Yes (1)	Yes (1)	Yes (5)	N.R.	Yes (7)	Yes (5)	Yes (birth)	Yes (5)	Yes (9.9)
Wu et al. 2009 [18]	Comp Htzg (stop codon)	Yes (?)	Yes (?)	No	Yes (?)	No	Yes (?)	Yes (?)	No	Yes (?)	N.R.	Yes (?)	No (28)
Poisson et al. 2018 [26]	Comp Htzg (missens)	Yes (4-5)	Yes (3,5)	N.R.	Yes (16)	N.R.	Yes (16)	Yes (3)	Yes (23)	N.R.	N.R.	N.R.	Yes (28)
Agarwal et al. 2003 [17]	Simple Htzg	Yes (?)	N.R.	N.R.	N.R.	N.R.	N.R.	N.R.	N.R.	Yes (?)	N.R.	N.R.	No (9)

N.R.: Not reported

Click here to access/download
Electronic Supplementary Material
supplementary_material.pdf

